

Heuristic Teaching Methods, Techniques, Forms, and their Interconnections

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Abstract: *This article examines heuristic teaching methods, techniques, and forms, along with their interconnections in the educational process. Heuristic methods are essential in fostering critical thinking and creativity among students, promoting active learning and engagement. The study categorizes various heuristic approaches and discusses their practical applications in classroom settings. By analyzing the relationships between different heuristic forms and their impact on teaching effectiveness, the research aims to provide insights into optimizing pedagogical strategies for enhanced student learning outcomes. The findings emphasize the importance of integrating heuristic methods into teacher training programs to equip future educators with the skills needed to cultivate an innovative learning environment.*

Keywords: *Heuristic Teaching Methods, Active Learning, Critical Thinking, Educational Techniques, Student Engagement, Pedagogical Strategies, Teacher Training, Creativity in Education.*

Among the important measures to be implemented in the social direction of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017, on the "Action Strategy for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan," is the formation of a new generation of educators for higher education institutions. This includes the task of educating a well-rounded individual who is morally and ethically mature, has an independent worldview, thinks creatively, is loyal to rich national heritage, as well as universal and national values.

In the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017, on "Measures for Further Development of the Higher Education System," it is indicated that "the educational process, the curriculum and programs of higher education should be further improved based on the wide implementation of new pedagogical technologies and teaching methods, and the qualitative renewal of the scientific and educational process of the master's program, as well as the introduction of modern organizational forms."

In such conditions, it is necessary to direct efforts toward forming specialists who possess the ability to fully respond to the demands of the reforms taking place in society, who can withstand competition in the production sector, adapt to drastic changes, and effectively operate at the level of the requirements set for specialists in the labor market. Today, the "discovery" of new knowledge and moral qualities in education is required to be carried out not only by the teacher but also by the students themselves, with the participation of the teacher.

Such rediscoveries occur during the work on the text, in the live communication between the teacher and the student, and are implemented through genuinely exploratory heuristic methods. The importance of well-organized methods in the lesson lies in their ability to meet the needs of young readers to express their opinions on what they have read and to share their views. Students participating in interesting heuristic methods discuss their thoughts and prepare to articulate their views. This ensures that their ideas are directed toward a clear and specific goal. During the lesson,

students develop the need to express their opinions and convince their peers of the correctness of their ideas. They acquire the skills to find evidence from the text to support their opinions, provide examples, and become accustomed to expressing objections. This encourages them to listen to their interlocutors, participate in discussions, deepens their need to enhance their knowledge, and expands their interests.

The modern development of heuristics began in the second half of the 20th century. This was linked to the emergence of cybernetics and the necessity of developing heuristic systems for scientific and inventive activities. By this time, D. Polya's fundamental research on heuristics had emerged, summarizing its previous development and outlining its prospects. He wrote: "Descartes contemplated a universal method suitable for solving any problem; Leibniz articulated the idea of a perfect method in the clearest form. However, the search for a universal, perfect method has proven to be less effective than the quest for the philosopher's stone, which turns base metals into gold. Nevertheless, such unattainable ideals are not in vain—although no one has ever reached the North Star, many have looked at it and found the right path." Polya was the first to discuss the necessity of early goal-oriented teaching of heuristic activity skills. He expressed the main idea of his works with the following words: "The process of solving a problem is the search for a way out of difficulty or obstacle—it is the process of achieving a goal that seems to be immediately unavailable. Problem-solving is a distinctive property of the intellect, and intellect is a unique gift of humans; thus, problem-solving can be regarded as one of the most characteristic manifestations of human activity." Gradually, the efforts of scholars shifted from the pursuit of a universal method to the systematic study of the laws governing human heuristic activity. "Regardless of the content of heuristics, it aims to establish the general laws of the processes that occur in solving all types of problems." Typically, heuristic methods for solving specific problems are contrasted with formal solution methods based on precise heuristic teaching methods. The use of heuristic methods (heuristics) reduces the time required to solve a problem compared to the method of enumerating possible alternatives without direction; as a result, the solutions obtained are generally not the best but merely a feasible set of solutions. The use of heuristic methods does not always guarantee the achievement of the goal. Sometimes, in psychological and cybernetic literature, heuristic methods are understood as any methods aimed at reducing the list or inductive methods for solving problems.

Heuristic activity is a field of study within the discipline of cognition; it is a special section of the science of thought. Its primary object is creative activity, focusing on the most significant problems and tasks related to decision-making models (in non-standard problem situations) and searching for new structures for describing the external world for an individual or society (based on classifications such as the elements of the periodic system by D.I. Mendeleev or the taxonomy of plants by K. Linnaeus). As a science, heuristics develops at the intersection of psychology, artificial intelligence theory, structural linguistics, and information theory.

The concept of heuristic education is defined as a conscious, structured creative activity in which theoretical and empirical knowledge is meaningfully summarized to create new knowledge. Heuristic-related concepts, principles, and semantic rules are presented in identifiable forms; "heuristic competence" refers to the ability to apply one's heuristic competence in practice. The structure of heuristic competence is defined and justified, comprising a motivational component that includes motivation for creative activity, a desire for self-improvement in mathematical activity and self-awareness, and the necessity to achieve goals; a cognitive component that includes knowledge of the theoretical foundations of heuristic activity and developed creative and logical thinking; and an activity component characterized by methods of action in non-standard mathematical situations, heuristic methods for solving non-standard mathematical problems, self-organization skills, as well as flexibility in thinking, reasoning, and willpower qualities.

The stages of developing heuristic competence are identified and described, including the motivational-diagnostic stage, cognitive stage, algorithmic stage, and research and creative stages.

In summary, the teacher's role is to create a creative and comfortable environment that encourages students' active participation, critical thinking, and motivation. Generally, heuristic methods and techniques are about fostering inquiry and exploration in the learning process. Key questions to consider include: What should be sought? What is known in this search? Can participants find solutions to tasks, problems, or challenges presented during the learning process? Where can the discovered analogs be applied?

By implementing heuristic education in the learning process, the following goals can be achieved:

- Education based on heuristics is student-centered, promoting personal inquiry, learning, and critical thinking.
- It leads to conscious assimilation through exploration, searching, and discovery.
- Heuristic approaches enhance students' creative thinking and intellectual potential by encouraging them to solve problems.
- Instead of merely retaining predefined content, students develop skills and competencies through individual work, relying on their strengths and capabilities.

Overall, heuristic education cultivates an environment where students actively engage, think critically, and develop the skills necessary for effective learning and problem-solving.

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